

Parametric representation of mixtures with two pure components

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July 22, 2019

Abstract

At the state preparation stage, pure states can be combined coherently or incoherently. Pure states can be represented by vector states and coherent combinations of pure states result in pure states. Incoherent combinations of pure states are mixed states and they can be represented by density matrices. Pure component states, in general, may not be orthogonal to each other and there are infinitely many sets of pure states that can be combined to yield the same mixed state. Mixtures (mixed states) with only two pure components are relatively easy to study. This work focuses on two-component mixtures to show that they can be parametrized by only two real parameters. The parameters define the orientations of pure component states in a two dimensional complex subspace and their associated weights. This means that all possible decompositions of two-component mixtures can be generated by two vectors and two associated weights that can be expressed in a parametric form with two real parameters. The proposed parametric decomposition procedure is quite general and it can be applied to quantum mechanical two-component mixtures and to depolarizing Mueller matrices that result as an incoherent combination of two deterministic optical systems.

1 Introduction

Let $|h_i\rangle$ be a complex valued N -component, normalized vector representing a pure state. A complex-Hermitian matrix $\mathfrak{H}_i = |h_i\rangle\langle h_i|$ also represents the same pure state. If two or more $|h_i\rangle$ vector states are combined coherently then the state of the combined system, $|h\rangle$, can be written as a linear combination of individual vector states:

$$|h\rangle = a_1|h_1\rangle + a_2|h_2\rangle + a_3|h_3\rangle \cdots + a_n|h_n\rangle, \quad (1)$$

where a_i are, in general, complex numbers.

If pure systems, represented by $|h_i\rangle$ vector states, are combined incoherently at the state preparation stage, then the state of the combined system can be represented by a complex-Hermitian matrix (density matrix), \mathfrak{H} , which can be written as a linear combination of individual matrix states (pure states), \mathfrak{H}_i [1]:

$$\mathfrak{H} = w_1\mathfrak{H}_1 + w_2\mathfrak{H}_2 + w_3\mathfrak{H}_3 \cdots + w_n\mathfrak{H}_n, \quad (2)$$

where w_i are real numbers such that

$$w_1 + w_2 + w_3 \cdots + w_n = 1 \quad (3)$$

Rank of \mathfrak{H} matrix given by Eq.(2) can take any value between 1 and N :

$$1 \leq \text{rank}(\mathfrak{H}) \leq N \quad (4)$$

Since, \mathfrak{H} is a $N \times N$ Hermitian matrix it may have at most N nonzero real eigenvalues, λ_i , corresponding to a complete-orthogonal set of N eigenvectors, $|\ell_i\rangle$, therefore, \mathfrak{H} has the following spectral decomposition:

$$\mathfrak{H} = \lambda_1|\ell_1\rangle\langle\ell_1| + \lambda_2|\ell_2\rangle\langle\ell_2| + \lambda_3|\ell_3\rangle\langle\ell_3| \cdots + \lambda_N|\ell_N\rangle\langle\ell_N|. \quad (5)$$

If $\text{tr}(\mathfrak{H}) = 1$ (\mathfrak{H} is normalized) then, $\lambda_1 + \lambda_2 + \lambda_3 \cdots + \lambda_N = 1$, and $|\ell_i\rangle$ constitute a complete-orthonormal set of basis, $\langle\ell_i|\ell_j\rangle = \delta_{ij}$.

Besides the state preparation (Eq.(2)) and the spectral decomposition (Eq.(5)), there exist infinitely many equivalent decompositions that yield the same density matrix, \mathfrak{H} . For example, let $|r_i\rangle$ be a complete set of normalized vectors that span the same N -dimensional space of $|\ell_i\rangle$ vectors. There may exist a decomposition of \mathfrak{H} with respect to $|r_i\rangle$ basis with associated weights, ρ_i :

$$\mathfrak{H} = \rho_1|r_1\rangle\langle r_1| + \rho_2|r_2\rangle\langle r_2| + \rho_3|r_3\rangle\langle r_3| \cdots + \rho_N|r_N\rangle\langle r_N|, \quad (6)$$

where $\rho_1 + \rho_2 + \rho_3 \cdots + \rho_N = 1$. It is worth noting that $|r_i\rangle$ vectors may not constitute an orthogonal set of basis, but they should certainly satisfy a completeness condition defined for nonorthogonal set of basis vectors.

2 Two-component mixtures

If the mixed state is a result of incoherent combination of only two distinct pure states $|h_1\rangle$ and $|h_2\rangle$ ($n = 2$), density matrix of the combined system can be written as:

$$\mathfrak{H} = w_1|h_1\rangle\langle h_1| + w_2|h_2\rangle\langle h_2|. \quad (7)$$

where $w_1 + w_2 = 1$.

If nonzero eigenvalues of \mathfrak{H} are not equal and pure states $|h_1\rangle$ and $|h_2\rangle$ do not coincide with the eigenstates, then $|h_1\rangle$ and $|h_2\rangle$ are not orthogonal to each other. If $|h_1\rangle$ and $|h_2\rangle$ vectors are represented in terms of N -dimensional standard basis, density matrix \mathfrak{H} representing the mixture is still a $N \times N$ matrix and, in general, it has N nonzero columns and rows. But, for such a two-term combination, rank of \mathfrak{H} is just two, i.e., only two columns (rows) are linearly independent and they span a two dimensional complex vector space. In fact, only two eigenvectors of \mathfrak{H} matrix, $|\ell_1\rangle$ and $|\ell_2\rangle$, correspond to nonzero eigenvalues λ_1 and λ_2 , respectively, therefore, spectral decomposition of \mathfrak{H} can be written as:

$$\mathfrak{H} = \lambda_1 |\ell_1\rangle\langle\ell_1| + \lambda_2 |\ell_2\rangle\langle\ell_2|. \quad (8)$$

This is an immediate result of setting $\lambda_3 = \lambda_4 \cdots = \lambda_N = 0$.

By adopting two dimensional standard basis to represent $|\ell_1\rangle$ and $|\ell_2\rangle$, \mathfrak{H} can be written in a 2×2 diagonal form:

$$\mathfrak{H} = \lambda_1 \begin{pmatrix} 1 \\ 0 \end{pmatrix} (1 \ 0) + \lambda_2 \begin{pmatrix} 0 \\ 1 \end{pmatrix} (0 \ 1) = \begin{pmatrix} \lambda_1 & 0 \\ 0 & \lambda_2 \end{pmatrix} \quad (9)$$

Eq.(7) and Eq.(8) represent just two decompositions. There exist infinitely many similar decompositions. It can be shown that for any two normalized vectors $|r_1\rangle$ and $|r_2\rangle$, that live in the same subspace spanned by eigenbasis $|\ell_1\rangle$ and $|\ell_2\rangle$, there exists a decomposition with associated weights ρ_1, ρ_2 , if $|r_2\rangle$ is a proper complement of $|r_1\rangle$:

$$\mathfrak{H} = \rho_1 |r_1\rangle\langle r_1| + \rho_2 |r_2\rangle\langle r_2|, \quad (10)$$

where, in general, $|r_1\rangle$ and $|r_2\rangle$ are not orthogonal to each other.

3 Parametric forms

It may be convenient to write all possible two-term decompositions in a parametric form. Let λ_1 be the greatest eigenvalue and let $|\ell_1\rangle$ be the eigenvector corresponding to the greatest eigenvalue. Consider a vector state $|\Psi_1\rangle$ which is obtained by rotating $|\ell_1\rangle$ by angles θ and ϕ in the complex two dimensional subspace spanned by $|\ell_1\rangle$ and $|\ell_2\rangle$:

$$|\Psi_1\rangle = e^{ix_1} \begin{pmatrix} \cos \theta \\ \sin \theta e^{i\phi} \end{pmatrix}. \quad (11)$$

There exists a vector state $|\Psi_2\rangle$, which is the complement of $|\Psi_1\rangle$ in the subspace spanned by eigenbasis $|\ell_1\rangle$ and $|\ell_2\rangle$ that satisfies the following decomposition with weights ρ_1 and ρ_2 ($\rho_1 + \rho_2 = 1$):

$$\mathfrak{H} = \rho_1 |\Psi_1\rangle\langle\Psi_1| + \rho_2 |\Psi_2\rangle\langle\Psi_2|. \quad (12)$$

Vector state $|\Psi_1\rangle$ is already defined by Eq.(11) in terms of θ and ϕ . The complement vector, $|\Psi_2\rangle$, and weights, ρ_1 and ρ_2 , can be found by calculating components of \mathfrak{H} matrix with respect to its own eigenbasis:

$$\mathfrak{H}_{11} = \langle\ell_1|\mathfrak{H}|\ell_1\rangle = \rho_1 \langle\ell_1|\Psi_1\rangle\langle\Psi_1|\ell_1\rangle + \rho_2 \langle\ell_1|\Psi_2\rangle\langle\Psi_2|\ell_1\rangle = \rho_1 \cos^2 \theta + \rho_2 x x^* = \lambda_1. \quad (13)$$

$$\mathfrak{H}_{12} = \langle\ell_1|\mathfrak{H}|\ell_2\rangle = \rho_1 \langle\ell_1|\Psi_1\rangle\langle\Psi_1|\ell_2\rangle + \rho_2 \langle\ell_1|\Psi_2\rangle\langle\Psi_2|\ell_2\rangle = \rho_1 \cos \theta \sin \theta e^{-i\phi} + \rho_2 x y^* = 0. \quad (14)$$

$$\mathfrak{H}_{21} = \langle\ell_2|\mathfrak{H}|\ell_1\rangle = \rho_1 \langle\ell_2|\Psi_1\rangle\langle\Psi_1|\ell_1\rangle + \rho_2 \langle\ell_2|\Psi_2\rangle\langle\Psi_2|\ell_1\rangle = \rho_1 \sin \theta e^{i\phi} \cos \theta + \rho_2 y x^* = 0. \quad (15)$$

$$\mathfrak{H}_{22} = \langle \ell_2 | \mathfrak{H} | \ell_2 \rangle = \rho_1 \langle \ell_2 | \Psi_1 \rangle \langle \Psi_1 | \ell_2 \rangle + \rho_2 \langle \ell_2 | \Psi_2 \rangle \langle \Psi_2 | \ell_2 \rangle = \rho_1 \sin^2 \theta + \rho_2 y y^* = \lambda_2. \quad (16)$$

where x and y are components of $|\Psi_2\rangle$ with respect to two dimensional standard basis.

The equation set can be solved for components of $|\Psi_2\rangle$ and for weights ρ_1 and ρ_2 :

$$|\Psi_2\rangle = \frac{e^{i\chi_2}}{\sqrt{\lambda_1^2 \sin^2 \theta + \lambda_2^2 \cos^2 \theta}} \begin{pmatrix} -\lambda_1 \sin \theta \\ \lambda_2 \cos \theta e^{i\phi} \end{pmatrix}, \quad (17)$$

$$\rho_1 = \frac{\lambda_1 \lambda_2}{\lambda_1 \sin^2 \theta + \lambda_2 \cos^2 \theta}, \quad \rho_2 = \frac{\lambda_1^2 \sin^2 \theta + \lambda_2^2 \cos^2 \theta}{\lambda_1 \sin^2 \theta + \lambda_2 \cos^2 \theta}, \quad (18)$$

In general, $|\Psi_1\rangle$ is not orthogonal to $|\Psi_2\rangle$. If $\lambda_1 = \lambda_2$,

$$|\Psi_2\rangle = e^{i\chi_2} \begin{pmatrix} -\sin \theta \\ \cos \theta e^{i\phi} \end{pmatrix}, \quad (19)$$

then, $|\Psi_2\rangle$ is orthogonal to $|\Psi_1\rangle$ for all θ and ϕ . In this case, all possible decompositions with parametrized states $|\Psi_1\rangle$ and $|\Psi_2\rangle$ become orthogonal decompositions.

It is worth noting that overall phase factors $e^{i\chi_i}$ do not appear in the parametric representation of the mixture, hence, any two-term decomposition can be characterized by only two real parameters θ and ϕ . Once the orientation of one component state is chosen, all other parameters are automatically determined in terms of θ , ϕ and nonzero eigenvalues of \mathfrak{H} .

4 Unitary operations and applications

Eigenvectors of \mathfrak{H} constitute column vectors of a $N \times N$ unitary matrix \mathbf{U} :

$$\mathbf{U} = (|\ell_1\rangle, |\ell_2\rangle, |\ell_3\rangle \cdots |\ell_N\rangle). \quad (20)$$

Any vector state $|\Psi_r\rangle$ that lives in the subspace spanned by the eigenbasis can be obtained as follows:

$$|\Psi_r\rangle = \mathbf{U}^\dagger |r\rangle \quad (21)$$

where $|r\rangle$ is any N -component normalized vector. If only two eigenvectors correspond to nonzero eigenvalues, only first two components of $|\Psi_r\rangle$ are nonzero, then $|\Psi_r\rangle$ can be written in a parametric form given by Eq.(11).

It is also possible to transform from $|\Psi_r\rangle$ to $|r\rangle$:

$$|r\rangle = \mathbf{U} |\Psi_r\rangle \quad (22)$$

Once the density matrix \mathfrak{H} is given or it is composed from pure constituents $|h_1\rangle$ and $|h_2\rangle$ with associated weights w_1 and w_2 (Eq.(7)), unitary transformation matrix \mathbf{U} can be found by calculating eigenvalues and eigenvectors of \mathfrak{H} . Starting with parametric forms of $|\Psi_1\rangle$ and $|\Psi_2\rangle$ given by Eqs.(11) and (17), parametric forms of $|r_1\rangle$, $|r_2\rangle$ and parametric forms of

ρ_1 and ρ_2 can be found. Hence, it is possible to write of all decompositions of \mathfrak{H} in terms of two real parameters θ and ϕ .

In general, it is possible to obtain infinitely many decompositions for a fixed θ by varying ϕ . Since, ρ_1 and ρ_2 do not depend on ϕ these decompositions correspond to the same weights. Similarly, by fixing ϕ it is possible to find infinitely many decompositions by varying θ . In some cases, at least one of the components of the preparation states, $|h_1\rangle$ or $|h_2\rangle$ may be zero. If zero components of $|h_1\rangle$ and $|h_2\rangle$ do not overlap, and if there exists some pre-knowledge about which component is zero (without knowing which vector state it belongs), it is possible to uniquely determine the original preparation states, $|h_1\rangle$ and $|h_2\rangle$, from the parametric forms of $|r_1\rangle$ and $|r_2\rangle$. For example, if it is known that third component of one of the pure states is zero, then by setting the third component of each vector equal to zero and inspecting for a consistent decomposition with a unique pair of values of θ and ϕ , it is possible to retrieve original preparation states $|h_1\rangle$ and $|h_2\rangle$ uniquely.

5 Conclusion

It is shown that all possible decompositions of a two-component mixture can be represented by two real parameters that can be interpreted as angles defining the orientations of vector states of pure component systems in a two dimensional complex vector space. The proposed parametric decomposition procedure is quite general and it can be applied to quantum mechanical two-component mixtures and similar formalisms such as depolarizing Mueller matrices. In polarimetry, depolarizing Mueller matrices may emerge as a result of incoherent combination of two deterministic (pure) optical systems [2, 3]. The methods for decomposing measured Mueller matrices into their nondepolarizing components may be important in applications of polarimetry [4]. For example, retrieval of pure components of a mixture can be used to improve quality of images obtained by radar polarimetry.

References

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